

KINETICS OF THE REACTION BETWEEN POTASSIUM PERSULPHATE AND THE ALKYL IODIDES. PART I. INFLUENCE OF SOLVENTS, ACIDS AND SALTS.

BY M. S. TELANG AND V. V. NADKARNY.

The solvent effect of alcohols, acids and the corresponding esters on the kinetics of the persulphate-alkyl iodide reaction, alternates in ascending the homologous series. This effect runs parallel with their dipole moments. A qualitative relationship between the specific catalytic effect of the cations, H^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ and Na^+ and their transport numbers is suggested. The chloride ion influences the kinetics much more than the corresponding SO_4^{2-} or NO_3^- . Amongst mineral acids, HNO_3 , HCl , H_2SO_4 and H_3PO_4 , the order of catalytic influence runs parallel with that of their ionisation constants although the parallelism is by no means quantitative.

Menschutkin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1890, **5**, 589) in studying the triethylamine-ethyl iodide reaction in a large number of solvents observed a qualitative relationship between the dielectric constant of the medium and its influence on the reaction velocity. Grimm, Ruf and Wolff (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, **13 B**, 301) in making a further examination of the Menschutkin reaction observed striking changes in passing through the following solvents, diphenyl ether, diphenylamine and diphenylmethane with $>O$, $>NH$ and $>CH_2$ groups respectively. Richardson and Soper (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1873) have given two empirical rules for solvent influence. Whenever there is a definite solvent effect, cohesion and polarity of solvents play an important part in influencing a reaction. In the present investigation to compare the relationship between the dipole moments of the solvents and the reaction velocity the following types of solvents are chosen: alcohols ($R-OH$), acids ($R-COOH$) and esters ($R_1-CO.O.R_2$).

“Primary kinetic salt effect” is observed with neutral alkali salts. In moderate concentrations of these univalent ions Bronsted-Debye-Hückel equation, $V = k \cdot C_A \cdot C_B \cdot (1 + \mu \cdot \beta_s)$ is obeyed up to at least $\mu = 1.6$. The values of F , the kinetic activity factor, have been calculated from the straight line graphs plotted from the reaction velocity against μ , the ionic strength.

Preliminary experiments have indicated that the conditions under which the kinetic measurements have been made are quite convenient for comparison and the reaction was found to be monomolecular.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Ethyl iodide was chosen as the alkyl iodide for all the comparable results in this work. Ethyl iodide was redistilled after drying with calcium chloride and preserved in the dark in contact with ignited silver powder, over calcium chloride in brown dropping bottles. The weight of a single drop was calculated by determining the weight of 20 drops. A normal solution of ethyl iodide in absolute alcohol was made by taking the required number of drops of ethyl iodide and then the strength of the iodide was checked by Stepanow's and Volhard's methods. The solution could not be preserved for more than two to three days without decomposition of the iodide taking place.

Recrystallised potassium persulphate was dried at room temperature in a vacuum over sulphuric acid. The purity of the persulphate was estimated by the ferrous sulphate method. The salts were of "Kahlbaum" purest quality and were used without further purification.

The temperature of the thermostat was maintained at $50^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ by means of Ostwald toluene-mercury electrical regulator, used in conjunction with an electrically driven stirrer. Solutions were made at thermostat temperature.

The iodine liberated during the reaction serves as a measure of the progress of the reaction. The reaction was arrested by dipping the flask containing the reaction-mixture in ice-cold water. The reaction was carried out in suitable round-bottom flasks fitted with efficient reflux condensers. After two hours' heating and subsequently arresting the reaction, the reaction-mixture was shaken in a separating funnel with benzene and the iodine present was completely extracted. The solution of iodine in benzene was directly titrated against 0.005N-sodium thiosulphate, the end-point being indicated by the complete decolourisation of benzene. The titration was carried out in a glass-stoppered bottle. At first the presence of the iodine in the benzene solution was apparent on account of its deep colour and gentle rotation of the liquid caused sufficient mixing with the thiosulphate. Towards the end of the titration, the bottle was stoppered and shaken after each addition of sodium thiosulphate and the end-point was reached when the solution was completely decolourised.

The velocity constants were calculated from the equation,

$$k = \frac{2.302}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$$

a , being the initial concentration of the ethyl iodide and the persulphate (which are taken in equivalent proportions) in g. equiv. per litre and x ,

the number of g. equiv. per litre of iodine liberated in t minutes. All determinations recorded were at 50° .

For each determination, the procedure was as follows.—

0.2*N*-Alcoholic solution (10 c.c.) of ethyl iodide, 0.2*N*-solution of potassium persulphate (10 c.c.) and solvent (5 c.c.) were made up to 100 c.c. with freshly distilled water, in a 100 c.c. measuring flask. The whole quantity of the reaction mixture was transferred to a round-bottom flask fitted with an efficient reflux condenser and lowered into the thermostat.

After two hours' heating, the reaction was arrested by dipping the flask in ice-cold water. If there was any iodine adhering to the walls of the condenser-tube, it was washed down into the reaction flask with benzene and the titration was carried out as described above.

For the determination of the salt effect, the reaction mixture consisted of 10 c.c. of 0.2*N*- ethyl iodide, 10 c.c. of 0.2*N*- potassium persulphate and x c.c. of 4*N*- salt solution, made up to 100 c.c. with distilled water.

TABLE I.

Solvent.	Vol. of <i>N</i> /200 iodine titrated.	$k \times 10^6$.	Dipole moment $\mu \times 10^{18}$.
<i>Alcohols.</i>			
Methyl	9.8 c.c.	207.10	1.67
Ethyl	7.9	165.00	1.72
<i>n</i> -Propyl	3.5	72.93	1.65
<i>n</i> -Butyl	5.1	105.50	1.74
<i>Acids.</i>			
Formic	0.8	15.35	} 1.4
Acetic	8.0	166.90	
Propionic	4.8	99.74	
Butyric	5.4	111.30	
<i>Esters.</i>			
Ethyl formate	0.6	9.82	} 1.4
acetate	5.3	109.30	
propionate	2.5	49.87	
butyrate	6.2	128.50	
Methyl acetate	6.9	143.90	} 1.8
Ethyl	5.3	109.30	
<i>n</i> -Propyl	2.2	44.12	
<i>n</i> -Butyl	2.8	57.54	

TABLE II.

Vol. of 4 N-NaCl added.		Vol. of N/200 iodine titrated.	Ionic concentration.	Velocity constant $k \times 10^6$.
0	c.c.	7.7 c.c.	0	161.2
2.5		13.0	0.1 N	274.3
5		15.8	0.2	335.7
10		25.0	0.4	537.1
20		37.7	0.8	824.9

TABLE III.

20 c.c. of 4N-R-Cl,	Vol. of N/200 iodine titrated.	ionic concentration.	Velocity constant $k \times 10^6$.	Kinetic activity factor (F).
HCl	71.2 c.c.	0.8 N	1632.0	8.588
KCl	44.6	0.8	984.0	5.178
NH ₄ Cl	38.7	0.8	847.8	4.462
NaCl	37.7	0.8	824.9	4.361

TABLE IV.

4N salt (20 c.c.).	N/200-I ₂ titrated.	Ionic conc.	$k \times 10^6$.
NaCl	37.7 c.c.	0.8 N.	824.9
NaNO ₃	16.7	0.8	354.9
Na ₂ SO ₄	16.3	0.8	347.2
KCl	44.6	0.8	984.0
†K ₂ SO ₄	16.6	0.8	353.0
CuSO ₄	30.05	0.8	648.3
Fe(NO ₃) ₃	55.2	0.8	1237.0

TABLE V.

4 N Na ₂ SO ₄ .	N/200-I ₂ titrated.	Ionic conc.	$k \times 10^6$.
2.5 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	0.1 N	211.0
5	10.8	0.2	228.2
10	14.0	0.4	295.4
20	16.3	0.8	347.2
40	26.9	1.6	387.6

† 80 c.c. of N-K₂SO₄ were taken as it is not possible to prepare 4 N solution.

TABLE VI.

4N H ₂ SO ₄ .	N/200I ₂ titrated.	Ionic conc.	$k \times 10^6$.
2.5 c. c.	19.8 c. c.	0.1 N	422.0
5	30.8	0.2	667.0
10	44.85	0.4	989.7
15	64.25	0.6	1457.0
20	69.5	0.8	1591.0
25	77.9	1.0	1805.0

TABLE VII.

20 c.c. of 4N acid, i.e., 0.8N ionic conc.	N/200-I ₂ titrated.	$k \times 10^6$.
HNO ₃	112.3	2747.0
HCl	71.2	1632.0
H ₂ SO ₄	69.5	1591.0
H ₃ PO ₄	25.3	544.8

DISCUSSION.

The reaction was found to be monomolecular. The reaction could be formulated in one of the following ways:—

Further work regarding the mechanism of the reaction is in progress.

To illustrate the parallelism between the alteration in the dipole moment of solvent and the reaction velocity, the moments of the alcohols in the homologous series are given. To compare the general solvent influence for three types of solvents—alcohols, acids and esters, the average values of the dipole moments are considered in Table I, dipole moment being a function of the polar group only, irrespective of the remainder of the molecule. However, the variations in the moments of the individual members in the same series are never very considerable.

Examining the values of the velocities in different solvents in a general manner, it is observed that the rates are in the order, acids > alcohols > esters, and the average dipole moments are in the reverse order, acids (1.4) < alcohols (1.7) < esters (1.8). (The values for the first members are neglected on account of possible induction effects.) It may be unjustifiable to draw a general conclusion with such limited data, but it does not appear improbable that the rates in this reaction and the polarity of solvents chosen are in the reverse order. Further investigations on the lines of Soper *et al* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1873; 1931, 2297; 1935, 1393; *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, **A** 140, 59, 71) are being carried out by us and will be published later on.

In order to ascertain the specific effects of different cations on the velocity of the reaction, experiments were carried out in solutions containing separately equivalent concentrations of potassium, ammonium, sodium and hydrogen ions, all being univalent. The velocity constants observed are given in Table III. For solutions of the same ionic strength, the values are highest in the presence of hydrogen ions and lowest in that of sodium. The reaction is so sensitive to hydrogen ions, that in more concentrated solutions of H_2SO_4 , deviations from the linear relationship is at once evident. This is probably due to the decreasing ionisation of H_2SO_4 with increasing concentration of the acid. Similar results have been found for

the monobromoacetate-thiosulphate reaction (La-Mer, *Chem. Reviews*, 1932, 10, 199), the mono-iodo acetate reaction (Holmberg, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1921, 97, 134), and for the persulphate-iodide reaction (Howells, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1939, 463). Observations were extended to include the anions of potassium and sodium and cations of copper and iron, by the addition of equivalent amount of their ions. The two cations are known to catalyse the persulphate-iodide reaction to a very great extent. It can be observed from Table IV that the chlorides of potassium and sodium are far more active in accelerating the reaction than the corresponding nitrate or sulphate and practically there is no difference in the activity of nitrate and sulphate ions. In the case of chlorides, probably the iodide from the alkyl iodide is interchanged and hence there is a marked effect on the velocity of the reaction.

The velocity constant-ionic strength curves ($k-\mu$) plotted from data in Tables II, V and VI converge at low ionic strengths. The extrapolated value for k at zero ionic strength, *i.e.*, k_0 is approximately 190×10^{-6} , the experimental value 161.2×10^{-6} is less than the former. The extrapolated value is used for calculating the relative kinetic activity factors, F , (Table III) from the equation $k = k_0 F$ (*vide* Brönsted, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, 102 169) k_0 has the same value whatever cations are present. The salt effect is in the sequence $H^+ > K^+ > NH_4^+ > Na^+$. The order of the activity coefficients of the salts employed is $HCl > NaCl > KCl$, etc. and the sequence of the viscosities of the chloride solutions of the same salts is $K^+ < Na^+ < H^+$, etc. Neither of these two sequences can be compared with that of the salt effect observed in this reaction, although in the persulphate-iodine reaction, Howells (*loc. cit.*) finds parallelism between the viscosities and the specific effects of cations. The velocities observed in this reaction decrease in the sequence of the transport numbers of the cations. (For the values of the transport numbers, see Washburn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 31, 322; Washburn and Millard, *ibid.*, 1915, 37, 694.) On account of the hydration (solvation) of the ions, the size of the ion-hydrate complex decreases in passing down the series, $Na^+ > NH_4^+ > K^+ > H^+$, and presumably, the speeds of the ions increase from Na^+ to H^+ . It appears that this order can be correlated with that of the specific catalytic effect of the cations employed.

Amongst mineral acids, the order is as follows: $HNO_3 > HCl > H_2SO_4 > H_3PO_4$. This order runs parallel with their ionisation constants and in the case of HNO_3 , the velocity of the reaction is highly influenced. It was suspected whether HNO_3 acts as an additional oxidising agent besides

potassium persulphate and with a view to settle this definitely, an experiment was carried out under identical conditions with HNO_3 instead of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ and there was no iodine liberated.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY.
RAMNARAIN RUIA COLLEGE AND
ST XAVIER'S COLLEGE, BOMBAY.

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